

D7.3 Gender analysis report v1

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Authors:

Hanna Kuittinen, Izaskun Jimenez, Xabier Uriarte

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Project summary

INGUMA Project aims to foster the development of bio-based materials and their acceptance by the public by relying on three main values sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics - the values of the New European Bauhaus.

The value of sustainability will be tackled by developing different types of bio-based materials from raw materials derived from agriculture residues and secondary raw materials from wood processing. Various types of materials will be developed: functionalized fibers, insulation material based on mycelium, resin-free insulation material based on wood fibers, bio-based adhesive for plywood, low-formaldehyde plywood board, wooden sandwich panels, and growth media for plants. In addition, these materials will be integrated into insulation panels and vegetated roofs.

The sustainability and circularity of these materials and solutions will be ensured by applying environmental criteria and digital tools that will allow users to make decisions on the most sustainable solutions available. Additionally, the materials will be tested according to European and international standards, as a first step in the commercialization outside of Europe (Canada).

The value of inclusion will imply the design of co-creation laboratories that encourage collaboration among stakeholders, fostering transparent communication and generating innovative ideas. These labs will provide a platform for engagement and a structured process for stakeholders to contribute their insights and actively participate in the development of bio-based construction materials. This way, the acceptance of the developed materials, products and solutions by end-users and consumers will be maximized.

The value of aesthetics will be accomplished by co-designing and constructing a community house prototype in the rooftop of an experimental building (Derio, Spain) and as part of test houses (Savonlinna, Finland) that will use extensively the materials and products developed.

Executive summary of the deliverable

“The promotion of equality between women and men is a task for the Union, in all its activities, required by the Treaties. Gender equality is a core value of the EU, a fundamental right and key principle of the European Pillar of Social Rights . It is a reflection of who we are. It is also an essential condition for an innovative, competitive and thriving European economy.¹”

This report presents the first gender analysis report of the INGUMA project. The objective of the report is to analyse gender balance of the management and team implementing the project as well as to consider how gender dimension could be better incorporated to INGUMA research and innovation (R&I) content. The gender analysis report is based on a gender monitoring survey answered by the INGUMA partners in November-December 2024.

The report shows how INGUMA mirrors the general situation of gender equality in R&I: it is close to be achieved among the research teams but far away when management positions are considered. In INGUMA, the participation of women is reaching 44% in the INGUMA team whereas women represent 20% of the General Assembly and 14% of the Executive Board. The integration of gender dimension in R&I content is a well known concept among INGUMA participant organisations, but according to the survey it was less clear how it could be implemented in the context of INGUMA R&I.

Based on the analysis, a set of essential actions are suggested to manage and improve the gender equality. The gender analysis reports to be delivered in month 30 and month 48 will monitor the progress towards implementing the suggested actions and analyse the progress in gender equality.

¹ European Commission (2020) A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, COM(2020) 152 final

Table of acronyms

Abbreviation	Description
AB	Advisory Board
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EIGE	The European Institute for Gender Equality
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
GEPs	Gender Equality Plans
IA	Innovation Action
JRC	The Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission
NeB	New European Bauhaus
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
R&I	Research and innovation
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
STEM	Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

This document presents the first edition of INGUMA gender analysis report. The INGUMA project adheres gender equality as a key value for successful completion of the project. The gender equality refers to the equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities of women and men². It means that the interests, needs and priorities of women and men are equally taken into consideration. In the INGUMA project, the gender equality is analysed from two complementing perspectives: gender balance in INGUMA governance structure and activities, and integration of gender dimension into INGUMA research and innovation activities.

The gender equality analysis of the INGUMA project is an on-going activity throughout the project and forms part of activities of the Work Package 7 (WP7) Management. This report presents the first edition of the gender equality analysis followed by two other reports in month 30 and month 48. The objective of these reports is to systematically analyse the gender equality taking into account both gender balance and dimension. In addition, the report suggest actions to improve gender equality in the project activities.

1.1 Gender in EU research and innovation activities

Gender equality is a core value of the European Union (EU), and the principle of equality of men and women with regards of equal salaries was established in the Treaty of Rome in 1957³. After, many EU laws have been established and broaden the concept of gender equality treating aspects such as working conditions, social security, access to goods and services, work-life balance, and maternity and parental leaves. The concept of equality was further reinforced and set as one of the fundamental values of the EU in the Lisbon Treaty, concerning Treaty on European Union, Treaty of the Functioning of the European Union, and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. The main aim to ensure:

- The right to equal pay for equal work or work of equal value,
- Equality of treatment and opportunities between women and men in all areas, including in the labour market, terms and conditions of employment, and career progression⁴.

The European Commission has adopted strategies for gender equality, the latest strategy covering the period of 2020-2025⁵. The strategy outlines the EU's commitment to achieving a "Union of Equality". It focuses on ending gender-based violence, challenging gender stereotypes, closing gender gaps in the labour market, achieving equal participation across different sectors, addressing the gender pay and pension gaps, and achieving gender balance in decision-making and politics. The strategy defines new measures to strengthen gender equality in Horizon Europe, such as the requirement of a gender equality plan from applicants and an initiative to increase the number of women-led technology start-ups. The strategy also ensures that part of Horizon Europe funding is dedicated to gender and intersectional research, understanding and addressing gender biases in the

² United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and Empowerment of Women (2024) Concepts and definitions. Available: <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/osagi/conceptsanddefinitions.htm#:~:text=Equality%20between%20women%20and%20men,men%20and%20girls%20and%20boys>.

³ European Union (2024) EUR-Lex, Summaries of EU legislation, Equality between women and men.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ European Commission (2020) A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, COM/2020/152 final

development of artificial intelligence (AI) and as well as on exposing gender stereotypes in all social, economic and cultural domains, supporting the development of unbiased evidence-based policies.

The broad measures defined by the EU gender equality strategy are implemented in the context of the on-going EU funding programme for research and innovation Horizon Europe. In Horizon Europe, gender equality is a fundamental principle aimed at creating a more inclusive and equitable research and innovation environment. Due to special characteristics of the research and innovation sector, targeted action is needed to overcome structural barriers and persisting gender gaps and inequalities. The key three initiatives of Horizon Europe towards gender equality include:

- **Gender Equality Plans (GEPs):** For certain categories of legal entities, having a GEP is now an eligibility criterion for funding. These plans must be public documents, endorsed by top management, and include dedicated resources, data collection, and monitoring, as well as training and capacity-building towards gender equality.
- **Gender balance:** Horizon Europe aims for gender balance in research teams, boards, expert groups, and evaluation committees. This includes a target of 50% women in these roles and using gender balance as a ranking criterion for proposals with the same score.
- **Gender dimension:** Integration of gender dimension into research and innovation content, which means considering gender perspectives in the research design, implementation, and dissemination to improve the quality and societal relevance of the outcomes.

In addition, Horizon Europe dedicates specific funding for gender and intersectional research, particularly under the Pillar II Cluster 2 “Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society” and developing inclusive gender equality policies within the new European Research Area through Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area programme. Horizon Europe also supports empowering women innovators under the Pillar III programme of the European Innovation Council.

The measures summarised in the Figure below are designed to ensure that all talents can thrive in a gender-equal working environment, with the goal of enhancing the quality and impact of research and innovation in Europe. Ultimately, they contribute towards the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 5 on Gender Equality and Women’s Empowerment, and indirectly to all SDGs, as gender equality is a necessary foundation across SDGs⁶.

⁶ European Commission (2021) Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Horizon Europe, gender equality – A strengthened commitment in Horizon Europe, Publications Office, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/97891>

Figure 1. Main novelties towards gender equality in Horizon Europe. Source: European Commission, 2021⁷.

1.2 Purpose and objective of monitoring gender aspects in the context of INGUMA

In the context of the INGUMA project, the objective is to incorporate gender equality as an integral part of the project governance and day-to-day activities, taking into account gender balance and integration of gender dimension into the INGUMA research and innovation activities. The goal of this report is to:

- Set the context by briefly presenting the current state of gender equality in research and innovation (R&I) in the EU, and relevance of integration of gender dimension into R&I content.
- Analyse the gender balance of the INGUMA project taking into account project's governance structure and work plan.
- Explore what integration of gender dimension in R&I activities could mean in the context of the INGUMA project.
- Identify and describe relevant actions to foster gender equality in the INGUMA project and their timeframe.

⁷ Ibid.

1.3 Data and information collection approach

To achieve the forementioned objectives, the following data and information collection approach have been utilised:

- **Literature review** for exploring the concept of gender equality in R&I activities and desk research on relevant INGUMA documents (Grant Agreement, D7.1 Quality Assurance Plan, Project Management Handbook and Ethics Management Plan).
- **Survey to INGUMA participant organisations**, for monitoring the gender equality and their perceptions on gender dimension. The survey was sent to all the General Assembly members (17) of the INGUMA project in November 2024. The survey questionnaire had three different blocks of questions: 1) Gender balance of the INGUMA project team, 2) Gender balance in the INGUMA activities, and 3) Integration of gender dimension into the INGUMA research and innovation activities.

2 Context: gender equality in R&I

This chapter provides a brief overview of the context concerning gender equality in R&I. The purpose of this chapter is to justify why gender equality is a necessary and important aspect, how there is still room for improvement, and how the integration of gender dimension into R&I is an important way of improving gender equality. The chapter also presents some endeavours to improve the gender equality emerging from the green transition and New European Bauhaus (NeB), for which the diversity and gender equality are essential values.

2.1 Overview of gender equality in R&I and construction sector

The She Figures publications, first released in 2003 and updated every three years, present data on **gender equality objectives in the field of R&I** in the EU⁸. The publications provide a comprehensive analysis to monitor the state of gender equality in R&I across the EU member states. It focuses on seven themes including gender equality of graduates, participation in science and technology occupations, labour market participation, working conditions, career advancement and participation in decision-making, and research and innovation outputs. The main conclusion of the report include:

- **Gender gap in research and innovation.** Women are still underrepresented in research and innovation, particularly in higher academic positions and leadership roles. Although women are reaching equality among doctoral graduates, 48.1% of doctoral graduates being women in 2019, they present 42.3% of the academic staff and only 23.6% of the heads of higher education institutions.
- **Science field matters.** There is a significant gender imbalance in certain fields, with women being more prevalent in social sciences and humanities, and men dominating in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM). In Natural Sciences, Mathematics & Statistics women graduates represents 44.9%, whereas in Engineering & Manufacturing & Construction, the women graduates are only 29.4% of all the doctoral graduates.
- **Career progression of women researchers.** Women face more obstacles in career progression, and often the proportion of women decreases at higher career stages. Women represented the majority of the population that is tertiary educated and employed as *professionals or technicians* in the fields of science and technology at European level (53.7%) in 2019. However, women are less represented among the population of employed *scientists and engineers* at the European level (41.3%). This gap is even larger when the self-employed professionals in science and engineering are considered: women present only 24.9% of entrepreneurs in science and engineering fields
- **Access to funding and inventorship.** Women researchers are less successful in accessing research funding. At European level, the funding success rate was higher for men than women by 3.9 percentage points, showing that gender differences persist in access to funding. In terms of inventorships (calculated based on the number of patent applications and the corresponding number of inventors), women were very under-represented in the EU 2015-2018, the ratio was 0.12, indicating that for every 10 inventorships held by men, just one (1.2) was held by women.

⁸ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, She figures 2021 – Gender in research and innovation – Statistics and indicators, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/06090>

The figure below summarises the key messages of the She Figures 2021 report.

Figure 2. Summary of She Figures key results. Source: She Figures Fact Sheet⁹.

The She Figures Report shows how European R&I policies promoting gender equality are having a positive impact, but at the same time there is still much work to be done to achieve full gender equality. The report identifies some positive trends, gender equality at PhD graduate level is almost reached and there is a small increase in the proportion of women holding the highest academic positions (26.2% in compared 24.1% in previous edition). However, important imparities still exist: women doctoral graduates in specific fields of study, such as Engineering, Manufacturing and Construction remain at low level (29.4%). The gender inequality in these fields can translate into “biased R&I output, loss of talent and growth opportunities¹⁰”. The integration of gender dimension in R&I content is of special relevance in Engineering, Manufacturing and Construction research, as it is still far from reaching gender equality. Integration of gender dimension into research and innovation content can address the inequality of the sector from inherent manner, changing the existing structures and biases still strongly present in the sector.

⁹ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, She figures 2021 – Tracking progress on the path towards gender equality in research and innovation, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/602295>

¹⁰ Ibid. Executive summary.

The **construction sector** is among the economic activities in the EU with the lowest share of women (10%) (see the Figure below)¹¹. In 2018, women summed up 12.0% of the workforce in civil engineering, 10.5% in construction of buildings and 9.4% in specialised construction activities¹². In some other construction-related areas the share of women was significantly higher: for instance in real estate activities women employees formed the majority in 2018 (50.3%), and architecture and engineering activities women represented 30.3% of the workforce. As in R&I, there is however a lack of females in managerial positions also in construction sector, which is leading to a significant gender pay gap.

Figure 3. Share of women by economic activity. Source: Eurostat, 2022¹³.

According to a recent report the reasons for low female participation are many fold¹⁴. First of all, it seems that women do not view the construction sector as an attractive or potential employer. In addition, an important share of female engineers leave the sector in the beginning of their careers discouraged from their early work experiences. The construction sector is still characterised by physical work at the construction sites, although automation and digitalisations has already changed the sector in this respect. The physically demanding professions can “label” the whole sector and some physically less demanding professions of the sector are overlooked by women.

¹¹ Eurostat (2022) Jobs with the highest share of women in Q3 2021. Available: Jobs with the highest share of women in Q3 2021. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/edn-20220304-1>

¹² European Commission (2023) Transition pathway for Construction. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/53854>

¹³ Eurostat (2022) Jobs with the highest share of women in Q3 2021. Available: Jobs with the highest share of women in Q3 2021. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/edn-20220304-1>

¹⁴ European Commission (2023) Transition pathway for Construction. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/53854>

2.2 Why integration of gender dimension into R&I is relevant?

The integration of the gender dimension into research and innovation activities involves considering sex and gender analysis throughout the entire research and innovation cycle¹⁵. This means considering both biological differences (sex) and social roles and behaviours (gender) in all stages of research and innovation process, from setting priorities and formulating questions to developing methodologies, collecting and analysing data, and reporting results. The aim of integration of gender dimension into R&I content is to enhance the quality and societal relevance of research by ensuring that it addresses the needs, behaviours, and attitudes of all people. It is important for several reasons¹⁶:

- Improving the quality of research results: Considering gender differences can lead to better and more applicable research outcomes as identifying differences in behaviours, needs and responses of different genders can lead to more robust and reliable results.
- Supporting innovation: By incorporating diverse perspectives, research can find novel insights and innovative solutions that might be overlooked if gender differences are ignored. This can drive technological advancements and wider uptake of the innovation in the market.
- Addressing gender bias: Integrating gender analysis helps to avoid biases in research results, ensuring that findings are applicable to a broader population, rather than being limited or biased towards one gender.
- Improving health and well-being: In fields like medicine and public health, considering gender differences is crucially important for developing effective treatments and interventions, which both men and women benefit equally.
- Fostering equality: This approach supports gender equality by ensuring that research and innovation activities do not further advance stereotype thinking or inequality between women and men. Integration of gender dimension in R&I content promotes inclusivity and equality of science.

The integration of gender into the R&I content is not a straightforward issue but comes with challenges. The previous research has identified at least the following factors hindering the progress of integration of gender aspects¹⁷:

- Lack of awareness of importance of gender analysis and lack of knowledge and examples how to adequately do it.
- Resistance to change in research organisations preventing implementing new policies and practises on how to conduct R&I activities.
- Lack of resources including funding, time, or appropriate expertise to do the additional efforts required by analysing the gender dimension in R&I.
- Lack of adequate data allowing the gender disaggregation and analysis of gender differences.
- Complexity of gender dimension making it difficult to integrate it into the R&I content in a meaningful and cost-effective manner.

¹⁵ European Commission (2024) Gender in EU research and innovation. Available: https://rea.ec.europa.eu/gender-eu-research-and-innovation_en

¹⁶ European Institute for Gender Equality (2024) Gender Equality in Academia and Research - GEAR tool https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/integration-gender-dimension-research-and-teaching-content?language_content_entity=en

¹⁷ Garcia-Campa, S. and Sanahuja, R. (2023) Gender Mainstreaming and RRI: The Double Challenge Chapter in Ethics and Responsible Research and Innovation in Practice. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-33177-0_12

To overcome these challenges, all the relevant actors including researchers, institutions and policymakers in different governance levels need to make joint efforts in promoting awareness, providing training, dedicating funding and resources and develop policies that support integration of gender analysis into R&I content. In the context of EU-funded research, the integration of gender dimension into R&I content was first introduced in Horizon 2020 by flagging topics across the programme as gender relevant. In Horizon Europe the integration of the gender dimension into R&I content is a requirement by default, unless the topic description explicitly specifies otherwise, setting the EU as a benchmark in global context.

2.3 The New European Bauhaus, green transition and gender equality

INGUMA aims to foster the development of bio-based materials and their acceptance by the public by relying on three main values sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics - the values of the New European Bauhaus (NeB). The NeB is an EU policy and funding initiative launched by the European Commission in 2021 aimed at supporting sustainable solutions for transforming the built environment and lifestyles under the green transition¹⁸. The NeB is targeted towards solutions that are not only sustainable, but also inclusive and beautiful, while respecting the diversity of places, traditions, and cultures in Europe and beyond. It aims to engage people at grassroots level living in neighbourhoods, incorporating views of various stakeholders into the process of design and implementation of the solutions and prioritising social inclusion, among other things.

In the spirit of the NeB and green transition, some initiatives aimed to foster gender equality have emerged:

- **Women of the NeB¹⁹** is an innovative initiative aligned with the NeB values of Inclusive, Sustainable, and Beautiful and aimed at inspiring positive change by advancing discussions around gender equality. This initiative strives to foster inclusivity and diversity, amplifying the voices of women across various backgrounds and fields from Europe and beyond. Encompassing those women shaping and co-creating spaces concerning the Built Environment, Architecture, Urbanism, Design and Creativity, and associated fields. Embracing the principles of intersectionality, Women of the NeB endeavours to create a comprehensive dialogue that resonates across Europe.
- **YesWePlan!** -project²⁰ has submitted a statement to the New European Bauhaus Platform to highlight the importance of Gender Equality in the field of Architecture and Civil Engineering for the success of the New European Bauhaus initiative. The statement declares how gender equality in Architecture and Civil Engineering is an essential factor for a sustainable and inclusive development of the built environment and thus for the success of the NEB approach. It continues by saying that although it is well known that there are gender specific needs and requirements regarding the built environment, they are not always considered, and consequently the built environment is far from reflecting female requirements accordingly. The better inclusion of women in the processes as designers, planners and users presents a large untapped potential to increase sustainable living. The project "YesWePlan!" is co-funded by the Erasmus+ programme of the European Union and connects different European partner organisations with the aim of

¹⁸ European Union (2024) New European Bauhaus. Website available: https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en

¹⁹ Women of the New European Bauhaus website (2024) Available: <https://womenoftheneb.com/>

²⁰ YesWePlan project website (2024) Available www.yesweplan.eu

sharing experiences and best practice examples for closing the gender gap in the professional field of Architecture and Civil Engineering.

- **The European Commission**²¹ has published a series of reports resulting from a study on the role of women in energy transition. The conclusions of this study include that women make up only 25% of the workforce in EU energy companies and 22% involvement in research and innovation. There is a need for 200,000 women to join the EU27 energy sector by 2050 to attain minimal gender balance, resulting to a concrete recommendation to promote STEM careers for women.
- **The Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission**²² in cooperation with the Dutch expert centre on diversity in the energy transition 75inQ, has concluded a study which emphasises the urgent need to reduce gender gaps in the energy transition. It sheds light on the often-overlooked impact of gender disparities in access to clean, affordable energy, emphasising the importance of inclusive policies in guaranteeing women's active engagement and representation in the energy industry, not just as customers but also as decision-makers and innovators.
- **The European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE)**²³ has published a report including identification and selection of ten good practices on gender mainstreaming in the policy areas of green deal in different EU countries and different policy governance levels.
- **OECD**²⁴ has drafted a set of recommendations to address risks and leverage the opportunities created by the twin transitions to advance gender equality for sustainable and inclusive economies and societies. The recommendations state that it is vital to address labour market inequalities and to ensure equal access to new job opportunities in green innovation and clean energy research and applications. Research indicates that diverse teams outperform homogeneous ones, and promoting gender equality helps expand the talent pool, bringing fresh perspectives and innovative problem-solving approaches to the teams.

²¹ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Gareis, K., Dashja, E., Hüsing, T., Popov, P. et al., (2024) Gender balance in the R&I field to improve the role of women in the energy transition – Final report and annexes, Publications Office of the European Union, available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/8283>

²² Murauskaite-Bull, I., Feenstra, M., Creusen, A., Koukoufakis, G., Della Valle, N., Shortall, R. and Stojilovska, A., (2023) Gender and Energy: The effects of the energy transition on women, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, doi:10.2760/511412, JRC132744.

²³ European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) (2024), Good practices on gender mainstreaming in the European Green Deal: Towards a more gender equal and greener Europe, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg

²⁴ OECD (2024) Harnessing the Green and Digital Transitions for Gender Equality: Insights from the 2024 OECD Forum on Gender Equality. Available: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/harnessing-the-green-and-digital-transitions-for-gender-equality_860d0901-en.html

3 Gender equality in INGUMA project

This chapter identifies relevant aspects of gender equality in the context of the INGUMA project. The gender equality includes two dimensions: gender balance of the INGUMA research team and activities, and integration of gender dimension into the INGUMA research and innovation content. **Gender balance** is the balance between number of women and men researchers involved in the project management and team assigned to implement the project²⁵, whereas the **gender dimension** implies analysing and considering the possible differences between men and women (biological characteristics as well as the social and cultural features) in the R&I content of the project.

3.1 Gender balance in the INGUMA project

3.1.1 Gender balance in the INGUMA project management and team

This section describes the project governance structure and presents the gender balance of the project management and project team. Gender balance is the balance between women and men in the research teams who implement a project. Horizon Europe projects should aim to have an even, 50/50 participation rate of both men and women amongst teams and in leading roles. In the case of the INGUMA project, the gender balance monitoring is relevant for the following elements of the project's governance structure Coordinator, General Assembly (GA), Advisory Board (AB), Executive Board (EB), Work Package (WP) leaders, Task leaders and Project team.

The following figure gives an overview of the governance structure of the project and the interrelations between the different governance mechanisms.

Figure 4. The governance structure of INGUMA project. Source: INGUMA, 2024²⁶.

²⁵ European Commission (2024) Gender in EU research and innovation. Available: https://rea.ec.europa.eu/gender-eu-research-and-innovation_en

²⁶ D7.1 Quality Assurance Plan, Project Management handbook and Ethics Management Plan

Coordinator

The Coordinator's role is to act as intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority and performs all tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. The Coordinator is responsible, on behalf of the project consortium, for submitting deliverables, payment requests, proof of deliverables and other documents through the grant management service. The Project Coordinator is also responsible for chairing all the General Assembly and Executive Board meetings, unless decided otherwise.

The INGUMA Project Coordinator is TECNALIA and the person coordinating the project is male.

Table 1. Gender balance – Project coordinator

Coordinator	Number	Share (%)
Women	0	0.0%
Men	1	100.0
<i>Total</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>100.0%</i>

General Assembly members

The General Assembly (GA) is the decision-making body of the INGUMA consortium. The GA members consist of one representative of each party, including Coordinator, Beneficiaries and Associated Partners.

Based on the D7.1²⁷ of the INGUMA project, there are 15 members of GA, including the Coordinator, 13 Beneficiaries and 1 Associated Partner. Out of 15 GA members, 12 are male and 3 are female.

Figure 5. Gender balance – General Assembly members

Table 2. Gender balance – General Assembly members

GA members	Number	Share (%)
Women	3	20.0%
Men	12	80.0%
<i>Total</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>100.0%</i>

²⁷ D7.1 Quality Assurance Plan, Project Management handbook and Ethics Management Plan

Executive Board and Work Package leaders

The Executive Board (EB) is the supervisory body for the execution of the project which shall report to and be accountable to the GA. The EB consists of the Coordinator and the Work Package (WP) leaders. The WP leaders are responsible for the performance of the seven WPs of INGUMA. The WP Leaders are committed to ensure the accomplishment of the technical objectives of each WP, report and follow deliverables and milestones to the Coordinator, reviewing and assessing the quality of the outputs, facilitating technical meetings required, archiving all documents related to the led WP and reporting progress and deviations of the workplan to the Coordinator and GA meetings.

The INGUMA Executive Board has seven members, including Coordinator and six Work Package leaders (WP7 is coordinated by the Coordinator). The following table shows that one WP leader is female and four are males. Two WP leaders are not yet assigned due to the fact that WP3 and WP4 start their activities at month 13 and month 16, respectively.

Figure 6. Gender balance – WP leaders

Table 3. Gender balance – WP leaders

WP leaders	Number	Share (%)
Women	1	14.3%
Men	4	57.1%
Not yet assigned	2	28.6%
Total	7	100.0%

Advisory Board

INGUMA plans to establish an external expert Advisory Board (AB). The AB members are proposed and steered by the Executive Board. The role of the AB members is to assist and facilitate the decisions made by the GA.

The AB has not yet been established, so the gender balance of the members is not yet known.

Task leaders

The Task leaders are responsible for the performance of specific tasks. Task Leaders shall be committed to ensure the technical follow-up of their specific task, coordination with other tasks in the same WP, assure the timely and proper execution of their tasks, report to the WP leader in case of any deviation or risk, leading the preparation of the deliverables resulting from their tasks, and prepare and delivery of internal task progress reports to the WP leader.

In INGUMA there are 34 tasks, out of which 10 are led by women and 21 by men. For three tasks, the task leader is not yet assigned due to the fact that the work has not started.

Figure 7. Gender balance – Task leaders

Table 4. Gender balance – Task leaders

Task leaders	Number	Share (%)
Women	10	29.4%
Men	21	61.8%
Not yet assigned	3	8.8%
<i>Total</i>	<i>34</i>	<i>100.0%</i>

Project team

The Project team are the persons implementing the INGUMA work plan in each partner organisation, including the WP and Task leaders and all experts working for the project. The total number of persons involved in INGUMA project is 126, out of which 55 (43.7%) are women and 71 (56.3%) are men.

Figure 8. Gender balance – Project team

Table 5. Gender balance – Team members

Team members	Number	Share (%)
Women	55	43.7%
Men	71	56.3%
<i>Total</i>	<i>126</i>	<i>100%</i>

The WP Project teams are formed by those persons working in a specific WP. As shown in the following Figure 9 and Table 6 the WP teams with highest participation of women include WP6

Communication, dissemination and exploitation (50%), WP7 Management (50%) and WP1 From raw materials to innovative materials kit (48%). On the contrary, the highest participation of men in WP teams can be found in WP3 Up-scaling of the selected processes and product manufacturing (73%), WP4 Demonstration of the selected solutions (67%) and WP5 Sustainability & circularity assessments (64%). It should be noted that these indicators are only indicative as the activities of some WPs have not yet started, and thus the assignments of persons to WPs may not be finalised.

Figure 9. Gender balance – WP teams

Table 6. Gender balance – WP teams

Team members	Women		Men	Total
WP1: From raw materials to innovative materials kit	Number	35	38	73
	Share (%)	47.9%	52.1%	100%
WP2: Social and environmental co-creation for the engagement of stakeholders and end users	Number	13	19	32
	Share (%)	40.6%	59.4%	100%
WP3: Up-scaling of the selected processes and product manufacturing	Number	11	30	41
	Share (%)	26.8%	73.2%	100%
WP4: Demonstration of the selected solutions	Number	5	10	15
	Share (%)	33.3%	66.7%	100%
WP5: Sustainability & circularity assessments	Number	15	27	42
	Share (%)	35.7%	64.3%	100%
WP6: Communication, dissemination and exploitation	Number	21	21	42
	Share (%)	50.0%	50.0%	100%
WP7: Management	Number	20	20	40
	Share (%)	50.0%	50.0%	100%

3.1.2 Identification of INGUMA activities with relevance of gender equality

In addition to gender balance in the team implementing the project, there are several activities of the project, in which gender equality can be promoted. These activities include presenting the findings or results of the project to scientific or other types of audience in the forms of conference presentations, scientific article submitted for publishing in peer-reviewed journals or presenting the findings of the project in non-academic events such as industrial fairs. The INGUMA project aims to encourage female speakers, or assigning female responsible authors to promote the presence and visibility of women.

The INGUMA project is also actively involving external stakeholders to the research and development process of new biobased construction materials in the forms of co-creation workshops, surveys and interviews. The gender balance of the external stakeholders participating in activities organised by INGUMA ensures that the perspectives, opinions, and expertise of women and men is considered in balanced manner.

Identifying those activities where gender balance can be promoted is essential for effective management of gender equality in the project activities. The following tables present the findings of the survey including the planned activities by Task.

Nine tasks have plans to present scientific articles and conference papers and additional eight tasks consider maybe doing so (Table 7). For these tasks it is important to remind the task leaders to take gender balance into account in authorship of the publications, and reinforce the role of women as responsible authors and presentators at conferences and event to extent it is possible.

Table 7. INGUMA tasks declaring plans to present scientific articles or conference papers.

Plans to present scientific articles and conference papers	Number of Tasks	Share (%)
Yes	9	26.5%
Not clear, maybe	8	23.5%
No	11	32.4%
N/A	6	17.6%
<i>Total</i>	<i>34</i>	<i>100.0%</i>

Eight tasks foresees activities involving external stakeholders and additional four tasks possibly involve external stakeholders (Table 8). In these tasks it is important to aim balanced participation of women and men as external stakeholders to ensure diversity of perceptions, opinions and feedback.

Table 8. INGUMA tasks declaring plans to involve external stakeholders.

Plans to involve external stakeholders	Number of Tasks	Share (%)
Yes	8	23.5%
Not clear, maybe	4	11.8%
No	13	38.2%
N/A	9	26.5%
<i>Total</i>	<i>34</i>	<i>100.0%</i>

3.2 Considerations of gender dimension in INGUMA research activities

3.2.1 How INGUMA could better incorporate gender dimension in research?

The gender dimension implies analysing and considering the possible differences between men and women, both biological characteristics as well as the social and cultural features, in the R&I content of the project. The integration of gender dimension ensures that the R&I outputs are adapted to needs and behaviours of women and men, and that the R&I outputs are benefitted by everyone. Integrating the gender dimension in R&I content is mandatory by default for RIA/IA actions in Horizon Europe. In the context of INGUMA, the integration of gender dimension means that the novel materials, products, and processes developed in the project are taking into account the gender of their producers, users, and beneficiaries (e.g. dimensions of insulation boards considering work ergonomics of women construction workers, toxicity related to manufacturing of materials potentially harmful for pregnant women, or differences of aesthetic likes between women and men).

Based on the survey to INGUMA participant organisations, many of them (12) are knowledgeable of the gender dimension concept, and know what it means. There were however 3 participants that had not previously heard about the concept (see the Tables below). Despite the high level of familiarity with the concept, only 5 partners had considered it in the context of the INGUMA project.

Table 9. Familiarity of INGUMA partners of gender dimension concept.

Are you familiar with the term gender dimension in R&I activities?	Number of responses	Share (%)
Yes, I am familiar with the term and I know what it means.	12	70.6%
Yes, I am familiar with the term but it is not very clear to me what it means.	1	5.9%
No, I have not heard about it before.	3	17.6%
N/A	1	5.9%
Total	17	100.0%

Table 10. Considerations of gender dimension in the context of INGUMA

Have you considered gender dimension in R&I activities of INGUMA?	Number of responses	Share (%)
Yes	5	29.4%
No	11	64.7%
N/A	1	5.9%
Total	17	100.0%

The partners who had considered gender dimension in the context of INGUMA, mentioned several aspects at different stages of R&I process, taking into account the project work, design of materials and products, co-creation workshops and INGUMA partner organisations' own policies and strategies to integrate gender dimension into R&I. Concrete examples of the before mentioned topics include:

- **Working during the project:** Protective cloathing/shoes in laboratory and pilot facilities are available for fits for women and men. There are equipment available for lifting and transporting heavy materials. Office spaces are equipped with chairs and desks which can be adjusted to any size.
- **Design of materials and products:** For raw material production aesthetics is not considered, but material is transported in quantities which are easy to handle. The desing of the final products must consider the gender dimension.
- **Co-creation workshops:** The design and implementation of the co-creation workshops, e.g. by aiming to identify gender balanced participants for co-creation workshops.
- **Partner organisations' strategies:** Integration of gender dimension in activities of the organisation, e.g. recruitment takes into account this by trying to balance the team and proposes same salaries to women/men, based on qualifications, not gender. Signature of the Women's Empowerment Principles (WEPs) developed by UN Women and UN Global Compact (Women's Empowerment Principles, WEPs) and introduction of the WEPs Gender Gap Analysis Tool to help us assess performance and set ambitious targets to promote equality, diversity, and equal pay.

The INGUMA partners who responded the gender equality survey suggested several ideas how the gender dimension could be better integrated into INGUMA R&I content. The ideas include:

- **Project management:** "Ensure that strategies and practices promote equity by including women in decision-making processes." "Setting up of a project-based Gender Group (GG) to carry out an evaluation on gender related issues related to the project." "Enhancing female participation in General Assembly meetings."
- **Research design:** "Include gender analysis in methodology. For instance, examine sex-specific data, behaviors, and impacts to ensure diverse perspectives are captured."
- **Product design:** "Considering that our products and materials could be used in DIY [do it yourself] market, they must include parameters such as its weight."
- **Stakeholder engagement:** "Actively involve women and underrepresented groups in co-design processes, advisory boards, and stakeholder consultations."
- **Capacity building:** "Provide training to project teams on gender-sensitive approaches and unconscious bias."
- **Dissemination and communication:** "Communicate findings in ways accessible to all genders and promote diversity in project materials and events." "Don't put it [gender] on the last slide, not the last bullet point, etc. If you consider it important it should be among the first 3 most relevant items and if somebody asks why, you should be able to explain it."
- **Indicators and monitoring:** "Develop gender-sensitive performance indicators and regularly monitor their implementation."
- **Policy alignment:** "My answer would be that men dominated R&I probably causes one of the biggest productivity gaps. As an example we could state the shift from single nationality teams to multi nationality teams that today tend to be the norm: nobody would question here what is better." "Align activities with EU gender equality policies, ensuring a transformative impact beyond the project's lifespan."

The ideas suggested form a rich basis for better integration of gender dimension into R&I activities of INGUMA. It also shows how gender equality matters and is a relevant for the INGUMA partners. This is an important point for departure for defining and implementing actions towards improved integration of gender dimension into INGUMA R&I.

3.2.2 Further perspectives for intergration gender dimension: Gendered Innovations initiative

Gendered Innovations²⁸ was a European funded initiative targeted to harness the creative power of sex, gender, and intersectional analysis for innovation and discovery and how better incorporation of these approaches can add valuable dimensions to research or even reveal new research directions. The project developed practical methods of sex, gender, and intersectional analysis for scientists and engineers and provided case studies as concrete examples of how sex, gender and intersectional analysis leads to innovation. One of the concrete tools the project developed is a method for incorporating knowledge about sex and gender into engineering innovation process, offering elements that could help considering when integrating gender dimension into R&I activities. The method consists of five steps that can be applied depending on the context:

- **Evaluating past innovation practises.** This step is targeted to recognition how development of past innovations and technologies may have served unequally women and men. The designers or developers create products for users whose interests and needs resemble their own resulting to “male default” as majority of the engineers in many industrial sectors are men. Also many products for use of everybody have unconscious male default, e.g. many video games are designed for men and boys, or assistive technology is utilising male voice by default.
- **Building the design team.** This step targets to ensure diversity in the design team. Including diverse expertise from science, technology, social sciences, law, humanities etc. can lead to more successful innovation.
- **Analysing users and markets.** It is important to understand who is benefitting from the innovation and differential effects of the innovation on women, men and gender-diverse of different social, socioeconomic and cultural backgrounds. The gender analysis should be grounded in empirical evidence of actual people and practises and needs instead of basing on gender stereotypes.
- **Obtaining user input.** Users and customers form a potential source of gender intelligence for innovation. The users can be incorporated to the innovation process through participatory research, surveys, interviews and objective measures derived e.g. from sensor based user data.
 - **Evaluation and planning.** Good practise requires an analysis of the outcomes considering benefits and challenges as well as lessons learnt how to develop gender expertise further.

The figure below summarises the process of integrating gender methods into engineering process.

²⁸ Gendered Innovations in Science, Health & Medicine, Engineering and Environment. Website available: <https://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/index.html>

Figure 10. Integrating gender methods into engineering process. Source: Gendered Innovations

The Gendered Innovations project also developed a checklist²⁹ for incorporating sex, gender and intersectional analysis into engineering research and innovation. It is formed by 24 key questions grouped in five blocks, including questions related to role of gender of potential consumers of the technology, relevance of sex, gender and other intersectional factors for the innovation, and identification of tools and gender expertise required. Some of the questions of the checklist may be relevant for identifying how gender dimension could be better incorporated to INGUMA R&I activities (see Annex 1 for preliminary selection of questions relevant for INGUMA). Actually many of the checklist aspects are already incorporated to INGUMA planning e.g. the utilisation of participatory co-creation methods, incorporating social lifecycle assessment in WP5, market analysis and exploitation plan in WP6 or inclusion of specific task for gender equality management in WP7, including this report. Another aspect challenging the utilisation of the engineering checklist in the context of INGUMA is the fact that the products and processes developed in INGUMA are not necessarily sold to consumer market but the key customers are rather intermediates (e.g. construction sector companies). The final beneficiary of insulation materials or green roofs are the persons living, working or utilising the building and these persons are often different from the ones who select or purchase the bio-based construction material.

²⁹ The full version of the Gendered Innovation Engineering Checklist is available: https://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/methods/engineering_checklist.html

4 Tentative actions for gender equality in INGUMA

4.1 Identification of critical actions to ensure gender equality in INGUMA

The tables below present a set of actions considered to be essential to bring gender equality forward in the context of INGUMA project. Based on the findings of current state of gender balance and integration of gender dimension into R&I content of INGUMA project, six actions are defined:

- Action 1: Promoting gender balance in INGUMA management roles and team.
- Action 2: Considering gender balance in selection of Advisory Board members.
- Action 3: Flagging and actively promoting the gender balance in the INGUMA activities.
- Action 4: Incorporation of gender analysis in studies and exploitation efforts of the project.
- Action 5: Organising an internal workshop on gender dimension.
- Action 6: Utilising gender neutral language in all project communication.

The actions suggested are subject to discussion and approval of the INGUMA Executive Board. They will be presented and complemented by the EB in the beginning of year 2025.

The action tables below include a title, target of the action, timing, responsibility and a short description of each action.

Table 11. Action 1 – Promoting gender balance in INGUMA management roles and team.

Action 1: Promoting gender balance in INGUMA management roles and team	
Target	Gender balance
Timing	M13-M48
Responsibility	ALL
The gender balance in INGUMA management roles and team shows that majority of management roles are occupied by men, 14.3% of WP leaders and 29.6% of Task leaders are women. In respect to the INGUMA team, the balance between women and men is 43.7% and 56.4%, respectively. Although the gender balance of the project management and team is unlikely to change significantly during the project duration, the INGUMA project promotes gender balance in occurrence of needing to introduce new members for INGUMA management roles or teams.	

Table 12. Action 2 – Considering gender balance in selection of Advisory Board members.

Action 2: Considering gender balance in selection of Advisory Board members	
Target	Gender balance
Timing	M13-M24

Responsibility	WP7 (TECNALIA)
<p>The gender balance is included as one of the selection criteria when selecting and inviting members for the INGUMA Advisory Board with a target of 50% of women. This objective is aligned with the Horizon Europe programme objectives, targeted to achieve, to the extent possible, gender balance in Advisory Boards related to Horizon Europe projects.</p>	

Table 13. Action 3 - Flagging and actively promoting the gender equality in INGUMA activities.

Action 3: Flagging and actively promoting gender equality in INGUMA activities	
Target	Gender balance and gender dimension in R&I
Timing	M13-M48
Responsibility	WP7 (TECNALIA), application ALL
<p>The objective of this action is to first identify those activities of the project in which gender balance can matter. These include activities related to communication of project results to broader audience (e.g. scientific publications, conference presentations, presentations at industrial or regional fairs, etc.) and activities involving external stakeholders (e.g. workshops, surveys, interviews).</p> <p>The following tasks plan to present INGUMA results in scientific articles or conference papers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 1.2 Lignocellulosic fibres from side-streams for applications • Task 1.3 Resin-free lignocellulosic fibres-based thermal insulation board • Task 2.1 Co-creation Community for Stakeholder Engagement • Task 3.1 Upscaling of lignocellulosic fibre production • Task 4.3 Demonstration in a demo space in Finland • Task 5.6 Application of digital passport to the developed bio-based materials • Task 5.7 End of life recyclability and reusability assessment of INGUMA products • Task 6.3 Dissemination Activities • Task 7.4 Monitoring of gender balance and gender analysis <p>The following tasks plan activities with external stakeholders:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 1.2 Lignocellulosic fibres from side-streams for applications • Task 2.1 Co-creation Community for Stakeholder Engagement • Task 2.2 Co-creation labs • Task 2.3 Monitoring and impact assessment • Task 3.1 Upscaling of lignocellulosic fibre production • Task 6.3 Dissemination Activities • Task 6.4 Exploitation of Project Results • Task 6.5 Networking and Collaboration <p>The leaders of these Tasks are reminded to take into account gender balance already at the planning stage of activities.</p>	

The INGUMA project promotes gender balance of the authors of the publications and encourages women to take leading role e.g. as responsible authors of the publications or presentators of the conference papers.

The INGUMA project targets to achieve gender balance in involvement of external stakeholders in workshops, surveys and interviews to ensure balanced views and diversity. When feasible, the results are analysed separately between women and men (e.g. survey results) to make the similarities and differences more visible.

Table 14. Action 4 - Incorporation of gender analysis in studies conducted in the project.

Action 4: Incorporation of gender analysis in studies conducted in the project	
Target	Gender dimension in R&I
Timing	M13-M48
Responsibility	Task 2.3 (FNR), Task 5.3 (ARDI) and Task 6.4 (ATL)
At least the Task 2.3 Monitoring and impact assessment, Task 5.3 Social impacts evaluation and Task 6.4 Exploitation of Project Results can analyse similarities and differences of participation patterns, behaviours, opinions and perceptions of women and men. These Tasks are encouraged to take gender/sex of survey, interview and workshop participants into account in the analysis.	

Table 15. Action 5 – Organising an internal co-creation workshop on gender dimension.

Action 5: Organising an internal co-creation workshop on gender dimension	
Target	Gender dimension in R&I
Timing	M13-M24
Responsibility	WP7 (TECNALIA)
Based on the initial gender equality survey, many of the INGUMA partners were familiar with the term of gender dimension in R&I activities and knew what it meant. However, there were some partners that had not heard about gender dimension before and most had not considered how to integrate it into the projects' activities.	
The objective of this activity is two-fold: 1) To inform INGUMA partners about the relevance of the integration of gender dimension into project's R&I activities; and 2) To co-create ideas and solutions how to better integrate the gender dimension into INGUMA R&I activities.	
WP7 (TECNALIA) will plan and organise the workshop based on the existing guidance and examples. The engineering checklist can be used as indicative guidance to support the INGUMA partners to think what integration of gender dimension could mean for their research activities.	
The workshop is organised as online or face-to-face event e.g. together with General Assembly meeting organised in M18 or M24.	

Table 16. Action 6 – Utilising gender neutral language in all project communication.

Action 6: Utilising gender neutral language in all project communication	
Target	Gender equality
Timing	M13-M48
Responsibility	Checklist prepared by WP7 (TECNALIA), application ALL
<p>Language and communication can play an important role in shaping attitudes, behaviours and norms in society, having potential for supporting and promoting gender equality³⁰. Gender-inclusive language means ‘speaking and writing in a way that does not exclude or discriminate against a particular sex, gender or gender identity, and does not perpetuate sexism or gender stereotypes’³¹.</p> <p>The INGUMA project aims to take the language inclusivity into account, and promotes gender-neutral and gender-inclusive communication in all written, spoken, and visual communication of the project. The objective is to avoid discriminatory, sexist and stereotyped language and depending on the context, and utilise gender-neutral or gender-inclusive communication. The gender-neutral communication is not gender-specific and considers people in general with no reference to women or men. The gender-inclusive communication is placing both women and men at same level and does not convey gender stereotypes. The guidelines prepared by the Council of Europe and European Institute for Gender Equality are taken into account by preparing a checklist promoting the use of gender equal language.</p>	

4.2 Monitoring of the gender equality

The gender equality of INGUMA projects is a horizontal activity and needing attention of the whole INGUMA project team and throughout the project duration. The progress of gender equality is monitored in two reports:

- Deliverable D7.5 – Gender Analysis Report v2 (M30)
- Deliverable D7.7 – Gender Analysis Report v3 (M48)

These reports will include analysis of gender balance and integration of gender dimension into R&I content, assess the progress of the actions suggested in this document, and if considered relevant, suggest new action to improve the gender equality in INGUMA project.

³⁰ European Institute for Gender Equality (2024) Words Matter Supporting gender equality through language and communication. Available: <https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/words-matter-supporting-gender-equality-through-language-and-communication.pdf>

³¹ Council of Europe (2024) Guidelines for the use of language as a driver of inclusivity. Available: <https://rm.coe.int/guidelines-for-the-use-of-language-as-a-driver-of-inclusivity/1680aec235>

5 Conclusions

This report presents the first edition of INGUMA Gender analysis reports, resulting from the activities of Task 7.4 Monitoring of gender balance and gender analysis. It is targeted to provide an analysis of gender equality at the end of the 1st year of the project. To analyse the gender equality, the report utilised secondary information from existing literature on gender equality in research and innovation (R&I) as well as collected primary data and information from the 17 INGUMA participant organisations through a gender equality monitoring survey, including questions related to gender balance of INGUMA team and activities, and the perception of INGUMA partners around the integration of gender dimension into project's R&I content. The key results of the 1st report include:

- The gender balance is not reached in the INGUMA management but the project team is balanced in terms of participation of women and men. The coordinator of the project is a man, and both the General Assembly and Executive Board are underrepresented by women, 20% and 14% of the members being women, respectively. The project team on the other hand represents in a balanced manner women (44%) and men (56%). These findings reflect largely the overall picture of gender equality in R&I: the equality is reached among researchers but not yet in research management.
- The integration of gender dimension into R&I content is an approach to improve the quality of research and gender equality of R&I by considering and taking gender into account in all research and innovation activities. In the context of the INGUMA project, majority of the partner organisations were familiar with the concept of gender dimension but much fewer had considered integration of gender dimension into the R&I content of INGUMA. The survey results indicated overall that the gender equality matters to INGUMA partners, and is an important aspect of project management. This was demonstrated by the variety of ideas how gender dimension could better be taken into account by INGUMA collected through the survey.
- Based on the findings of the gender equality situation, a set of six targeted actions are planned, including timing and responsibilities. These tentative actions are still subject of discussion and approval of INGUMA Executive Board.
- The gender equality of the INGUMA project is a horizontal activity and needing attention of the whole INGUMA project team and throughout the project duration. The progress of gender equality is monitored in two follow-up reports: D7.5 – Gender Analysis Report v2 (M30) and D7.7 – Gender Analysis Report v3 (M48).

References

- [1] European Commission (2020) A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, COM(2020) 152 final
- [2] United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and Empowerment of Women (2024) Concepts and definitions. Available: <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/osagi/conceptsanddefinitions.htm#:~:text=Equality%20between%20women%20and%20men,men%20and%20girls%20and%20boys.>
- [3,4] European Union (2024) EUR-Lex, Summaries of EU legislation, Equality between women and men.
- [5] European Commission (2020) A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, COM/2020/152 final
- [6,7] European Commission (2021) Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Horizon Europe, Gender equality – A strengthened commitment in Horizon Europe, Publications Office, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/97891>
- [8] European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, She figures 2021 – Gender in research and innovation – Statistics and indicators, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/06090>
- [9,10] European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2021) She figures 2021 – Tracking progress on the path towards gender equality in research and innovation, Publications Office, , <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/602295>
- [11,13] Eurostat (2022) Jobs with the highest share of women in Q3 2021. Available: Jobs with the highest share of women in Q3 2021. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/edn-20220304-1>
- [12,14] European Commission (2023) Transition pathway for Construction. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/53854>
- [15] European Commission (2024) Gender in EU research and innovation. Available: https://rea.ec.europa.eu/gender-eu-research-and-innovation_en
- [16] European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) (2024) Gender Equality in Academia and Research - GEAR tool https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/integration-gender-dimension-research-and-teaching-content?language_content_entity=en
- [17] Garcia-Campa, S. and Sanahuja, R. (2023) Gender Mainstreaming and RRI: The Double Challenge Chapter in Ethics and Responsible Research and Innovation in Practice. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-33177-0_12
- [18] European Union (2024) New European Bauhaus. Website available: https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en
- [19] Women of the New European Bauhaus website (2024) Available: <https://womenoftheneb.com/>
- [20] YesWePlan project website (2024) Available www.yesweplan.eu
- [21] European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Gareis, K., Dashja, E., Hüsing, T., Popov, P. et al. (2024) Gender balance in the R&I field to improve the role of women in the energy transition – Final report and annexes, Publications Office of the European Union, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/8283>
- [22] Murauskaite-Bull, I., Feenstra, M., Creusen, A., Koukoufikis, G., Della Valle, N., Shortall, R. and Stojilovska, A. (2023) Gender and Energy: The effects of the energy transition on women, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, doi:10.2760/511412, JRC132744.

[23] European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) (2024) Good practices on gender mainstreaming in the European Green Deal: Towards a more gender equal and greener Europe, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg

[24] OECD (2024) Harnessing the Green and Digital Transitions for Gender Equality: Insights from the 2024 OECD Forum on Gender Equality. Available: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/harnessing-the-green-and-digital-transitions-for-gender-equality_860d0901-en.html

[25] European Commission (2024) Gender in EU research and innovation. Available: https://rea.ec.europa.eu/gender-eu-research-and-innovation_en

[26-27] INGUMA (2024) D7.1 Quality Assurance Plan, Project Management handbook and Ethics Management Plan

[28-29] Gendered Innovations in Science, Health & Medicine, Engineering and Environment. Website available: <https://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/index.html>

[30] European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) (2024) Words Matter Supporting gender equality through language and communication. Available: <https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/words-matter-supporting-gender-equality-through-language-and-communication.pdf>

[31] Council of Europe (2024) Guidelines for the use of language as a driver of inclusivity. Available: <https://rm.coe.int/guidelines-for-the-use-of-language-as-a-driver-of-inclusivity/1680aec235>

Annex 1: Gendered Innovations - Engineering Checklist

This checklist³² is intended for researchers addressing the development of technologies and related products, services, infrastructures, or processes. It provides a set of key questions for incorporating sex, gender and intersectional analyses into engineering—as a basis for developing gendered innovations. The checklist below includes a selection of 10 questions:

1. Potential users of technology have different characteristics (gender identities, sex, age, ethnicity, profession, occupation, education, income, household and living arrangements, familiarity with and attitudes towards technology, etc.) What role, if any, do these factors play with regard to the developed technology?
2. Are there any anatomical and physiological differences between women, and men, and non-binary individuals that should be considered (e.g., in height, strength, range of motion, in vision, hearing, voice pitch, sense of touch, smell, and taste, muscular tension, temperature perception, etc.)?
3. What are the potential application areas of the technology (e.g., professional life, leisure activities, home, etc.)? Do these contexts suggest different patterns of use by different groups of potential users?
4. Might different groups of potential users have different expectations regarding the technology? Do certain features of previous innovations reinforce existing gender inequalities, gender norms, or stereotypes?
5. Might different groups of potential users have different expectations regarding the exterior design?
6. Might different groups of potential users have different expectations regarding the features and functions?
7. Is it possible and/or necessary to establish a usability lab? What additional tools might you use (e.g., questionnaires, workshops, etc.) to achieve user feedback?
8. Have you ensured diversity within test groups (in terms of age, sex, gender identity, etc.)?
9. Is the project exploitation plan missing potential opportunities by not addressing sex, gender, or intersectional factors sufficiently? Where might analysing these factors open up new business opportunities through Gendered Innovation?
10. In which other ways gender aspects could better be integrated to the project work (e.g., project sustainability; stakeholder engagement and community relations; workforce development and skill-building; health and safety, event organisation, etc.)?

³² The full version is available: http://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/methods/engineering_checklist.html